

Syntheses of 2-Phenylthio- and 2-Chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone

ROBERT W. GRAY and ANDRE S. DREIDING*

Organisch-Chemisches Institut der Universität Zürich, Rämistrasse 74-76, 8001 Zürich, Switzerland

4-*exo*-Bromo-7,7-dichloro-bicyclo [3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one (III) reacted with the sodium salt of thiophenol to give 2-phenylthio-3,7-dehydrotropone (IV). Treatment of III with triethylamine at low temperature allowed the observation of the characteristic ¹H-NMR. signals of 2-chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone (V), which was converted with diisopropylamine into 2-diisopropylamino-3,7-dehydrotropone (VI).

RECENTLY we reported^{1,2} the syntheses of several 3,7-dehydrotropone(II) substituted in the 2-position by alkyl, aryl or dialkylamino groups as well as of 2-chloro-4,5-benzo-3,7-dehydrotropone. The final step used in the preparation of these interestingly conjugated and strained substances was the treatment of a suitable 4-*exo*-7-*exo*-dihalo-bicyclo [3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one (I) with 2 equivalents of a base at low temperature, the ease of isolation of the resulting 3,7-dehydrotropone (II) being dependant on the substituent at C(2).

X = halogen
R = alkyl, aryl or dialkylamino

Continuing our studies on these compounds we now describe the syntheses of two further members in the 3,7-dehydrotropone series, both substituted in the 2-position, one by a phenylthio and the other by a chloro group.

As precursor for the syntheses of the two title compounds served 4-*exo*-bromo-7,7-dichloro-bicyclo [3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one (III), m.p. 80-81°, which had been previously prepared¹ by treatment of 7,7-dichloro-bicyclo [3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one³ with 1 equivalent of N-bromosuccinimide. Reaction of III with the sodium salt of thiophenol in the presence of 2 equivalents of triethylamine in ether at low temperature and repeated chromatography yielded 11% of 2-phenylthio-3,7-dehydrotropone (IV) as a moderately stable orange oil. The structure of IV is evident from the following spectral data: a) The intense UV absorptions at 232 and

325 nm show strong conjugation. b) The IR. -band at 1760 with a shoulder at 1735 cm⁻¹ is due to the carbonyl group and the one at 1570 cm⁻¹ may possibly

IV : R = SC₆H₅
V : R = Cl
VI : R = N(iPr)₂

be attributed to a polarised double bond†, c) The ¹H-NMR. -spectrum exhibits 1 proton doublets at δ = 6.09 (J=4 Hz) and 6.32 ppm. (J=2.3 Hz) for H-C(4) and H-C(6), respectively, and a broad 6 proton multiplet at δ = 7.4-7.8 for the protons on the phenyl ring together with H-C(5), the low field position of the latter signal being the result of alternating ^π-electron density at positions 4, 5 and 6 (compare lit.²). d) The mass spectrum shows peaks at m/e 212 (M⁺) and fragments at m/e 184 (loss of CO), 135 (base peak, loss of C₆H₅) and 107 (loss of CO and C₆H₅), all in accordance with structure IV.

The synthesis of 2-chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone (V) proved more difficult due to its instability at ambient temperatures; V could be observed in solution but not isolated. On treating III in deuteriochloroform with 2 equivalents of triethylamine at -40° in a NMR.-tube the gradual disappearance of signals due to III was observed, while three new signals characteristic for V appeared. These new signals are a doublet at δ = 6.84 ppm (J=2 Hz) for H-C(6), a doublet at δ = 7.60 ppm (J=4 Hz) for H-C(4) and a double doublet at δ = 8.27 ppm (J=4 & 2 Hz) for H-C(5)). 2-Chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone(V) appears to be thermally unstable, since warming of the reaction solution to -30° caused these signals to vanish slowly, with no new signals observable.

† This band is situated at somewhat lower wavelengths than those observed previously with other members of the 3,7-dehydrotropone series² (1595-1630 cm⁻¹).

Treatment of III in dilute chloroform solution with 2 equivalents of triethylamine at -40° , until thin layer chromatography indicated absence of the educt (III), followed by addition of 1 equivalent of diisopropylamine at the same temperature resulted in a 13% yield of 2-diisopropylamino-3,7-dehydrotropone (VI). This permits the interpretation that 2-chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone (V) suffers nucleophilic attack by diisopropylamine to give an intermediate such as VII, which subsequently

loses chloride ion. It is probable that IV is formed via the intermediate (VIII) and that the previously described¹ procedure for making VI also passes through VII. A similar nucleophilic displacement is known⁴ in the tropone series.

Experimental

The abbreviations used in the following text have been described previously⁵.

2-Phenylthio-3,7-dehydrotropone (IV). To a solution of 110 mg (1 mmol) thiophenol in 3 ml ether was added 48 mg (1.1 mmol; 55% dispersion in oil) sodium hydride. After evolution of hydrogen had ceased (15 min), the mixture was cooled to -70° and 250 mg (1 mmol) 4-*exo*-bromo-7,7-dichloro-bicyclo[3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one (III) followed by 202 mg (0.28 ml; 2 mmol) triethylamine was added. On warming to room temperature the colour darkened. Filtration through a 10 g silica gel column eluting with chloroform gave 70 mg of a red gum which was purified by repeated preparative chromatography (acetone-hexane 3:7) yielding 23 mg (11%) IV as an orange oil which resisted crystallisation. UV (EtOH): Max. 232 (19,273); 325 (15,000). IR (CHCl₃): 3063m; 3040m; 3015m; 2930w; 2860w; 1760vs (C=O); 1735sh; 1570s (aromatic); 1521m; 1480m; 1447m; 1370m; 1335s; 1185s; 1140s; 1117m; 1087m; 1062m; 1025m; 1000w; 970m; 920m; 835s. ¹H-NMR (100 MHz; CDCl₃): δ =7.8–7.4 m. 6H (5H-Ar and H-C(5)); 6.32 d (J=2.3), 1H (H-C(6)); 6.09 d (J=4), 1H (H-C(4)). MS: 212 (62) (M⁺); 184(25) (M⁺-CO); 135(100) (M⁺-C₆H₅); 107(22) (M⁺-CO, C₆H₅).

2-Chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone (V).—A solution of 27 mg (0.12 mmol) 4-*exo*-bromo-7,7-dichloro-bicyclo[3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one (III) in 0.4 ml deuteriochloroform

and 3 drops tetramethylsilane was made up in an NMR-tube and cooled to -40° . After measuring the ¹H-NMR spectrum (100 MHz) which showed the clean signals of III, a solution of 20.2 mg (0.2 mmol) triethylamine in 0.3 ml deuteriochloroform was added at this temperature and the spectrum measured again. The following signals due to V could be seen: ¹H-NMR. (100 MHz; CDCl₃) at -40° : δ =8.27 dd (J=4, 2) (H-C(5)); 7.60 d (J=4) (H-C(4)), 6.84 d (J=2) (H-C(6)). Measured on the spectrum of the solution before the addition of the base and considering the dilution on adding the reagent, the intensities of these signals suggest a conversion to V of about 30%. Two small broad peaks at 6.8–6.7 and 6.6–6.5 due to triethylamine hydrochloride and hydrobromide could be seen and the rest of the spectrum from 6.4 to 1.0 showed signals due to about 30% unchanged educt (III) and triethylamine. On warming to -30° the signals due to V became much less intense; after 5 min at this temperature they disappeared completely and the solution in the NMR-tube had become brown-black.

Conversion of 2-Chloro-3,7-dehydrotropone (V) to 2-Diisopropylamino-3,7-dehydrotropone (VI)—A stirred solution of 92 mg (0.36 mmol) 4-*exo*-bromo-7,7-dichloro-bicyclo[3.2.0] hept-2-en-6-one¹ (III) in 50 ml chloroform at -60° was treated with 0.1 ml (72.6 mg; 0.72 mmol) triethylamine and kept at -40° until TLC. (CHCl₃) indicated the absence of educt III (ca. 1 h). To the now pale yellow solution at -40° was added 0.05 ml (35.7 mg; 0.36 mmol) diisopropylamine and the mixture allowed to warm up slowly to RT. whereupon the colour darkened. Evaporation of the solvent gave a brown oil which was purified by prep. TLC. (CHCl₃) yielding 10 mg (13%) VI, identical (m.p., mixed m.p.) with a previously described sample¹.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung and by Sandoz AG, Basel.

References

- C. E. DAHL, R. W. GRAY and A. S. DREIDING, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 57, 1169.
- B. SZRECHNER and A. S. DREIDING, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1976, 59, 21.
- H. C. STEVENS, D. A. REICH, D. R. BRANDT, K. R. FOUNTAIN and E. J. GAUGHAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 5257; L. GHOSZ, R. MONTAIGNE and P. MOLLET, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 135.
- J. D. HOBSON and J. R. MALPASS, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1969, 1499.
- M. KARPFF and A. S. DREIDING, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 58, 2409.